

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AND TEACHERS' JOB EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RIVERS STATE

Glory Nwerekamma Augustine TOBINS

Department of General Studies, School of Foundation and General Studies
Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rivers State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT: This study investigated the relationship between occupational stress and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The research design was correlational, with 656 participants selected from a population of 6,839 teachers. The "Occupational Stress and Teachers' Job Effectiveness" questionnaire was used to collect data, with a Cronbach Alpha Co-efficient of .78 for reliability assessment. The findings showed that lack of time management, excessive workload, and other factors contributed to reduced job performance. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient revealed a positive correlation between occupational stress and reduced job performance. The study concluded that occupational stress affects teachers' performance and recommended that school principals take necessary actions to manage workload, provide incentives, and embrace technology to enhance teaching and learning. The study suggested that addressing occupational stress can lead to improved job effectiveness, student engagement, and overall educational development.

Keywords: Occupational Stress, Teachers, Job Effectiveness.

Reference to this paper should be made as follows:

Tobins, G. N. A. (2024). Occupational stress and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Leadership, Quality Education and African Development*, 1(1), 000-000.

Copyright © 2024 IJLQEAD

INTRODUCTION

Efficiency is the key to achieving excellence in any educational institution. Efficiency refers to the ability to produce a desired outcome, which results in fulfilling objectives and goals whilst enhancing the output that leads towards improved social, economic, political and technological advancements within today's world where technology has become integral to all aspects of work. Teachers with active minds who demonstrate resourcefulness along with competency are critical factors contributing largely towards increased efficiency during instructional processes (Usha, 2013). Stress can have both positive and negative effects on teachers, affecting them physically and emotionally. On the one hand, it can motivate action and bring about a new perspective. On the other hand, stress may also lead to feelings of distrust, rejection, anger or depression which result in health issues such as headaches, stomach upset, lack of concentration etc. According to Akinboye et al. (2002), WHO considers stress a global epidemic since 90% of physicians visit were attributed to this condition while 40% of employee turnover cases are due to work-related stresses. Stress affects individuals' physical, mental, social, emotional, and spiritual well-being, as a result, it compromises productivity. Teachers experience academic pressure, strain, tension

& anxiety disrupting goals achievement. However, equal workload among colleagues won't guarantee contentment amidst students hence leading to dissatisfaction in experts handling different classes.

Occupational stress is a pervasive issue among teachers in public secondary schools in Rivers State, posing a significant threat to their mental health, physical well-being, and professional effectiveness. The sources of this stress are multifaceted and far-reaching, encompassing the physical demands of commuting to work, the emotional toll of extended hours at school, and the harsh environmental conditions that further exacerbate the strain on educators. Moreover, the excessive workload placed upon teachers takes a devastating toll on their emotional well-being, as they struggle to cope with the pressure to achieve targets within tight schedules. This sense of being overburdened and anxious is further compounded by family challenges, such as balancing household responsibilities with the demands of their teaching jobs, all while struggling to make ends meet on paltry salaries amidst the high cost of living expenses prevalent in Nigeria.

The situation is further aggravated by poor morale, brought about by internal politics and the lack of support from local management teams during inspection processes. This toxic environment creates a never-ending cycle of stress, making it challenging for teachers to navigate their work effectively. It is imperative that urgent attention is given to address the welfare and well-being of teachers, ensuring they receive adequate support and self-care to manage their occupational stress. In the educational system, teachers are vital to a school's achievement as they serve as key facilitators and managers of classroom activities. As principal change agents for students' success or lack thereof in their academic endeavors, educators must strive to accomplish the goals of education effectively. Competent teaching is an outstanding feature of superior-quality learning environments. According to Raghu (2004), some factors that affect teacher effectiveness include intelligence levels, attitudes towards pedagogy, experience level, scholastic qualifications achieved personality traits and mental health status among others.

The effectiveness of a teacher's job refers to their ability to fulfill the duties outlined in their scheme of service, which includes tasks such as preparing lesson plans/notes, delivering lessons effectively and on time, evaluating classroom performance and managing student work. Time management is important for teachers as it helps them prioritize tasks that are most crucial within set deadlines. By utilizing effective strategies like creating daily to-do-lists prioritized by importance or setting strict deadlines while avoiding external distractions can help increase productivity and minimize occupational stress caused by poor time usage among educators. Therefore inadequate planning may reduce students' achievement rates across various academic levels when adequate attention isn't paid towards improving the institution's teaching system through proper resource allocation measures aimed at finding solutions ranging from more training opportunities outside classrooms where they receive instructional advice etc., all geared towards enhancing quality education delivery services provided every year throughout different grades.

When teachers are overloaded with work, they may experience burnout caused by stress. This can have lasting impacts on their well-being and health. Burnt-out teachers become disengaged from their jobs, which leads to decreased job satisfaction and a higher turnover rate (Mullen et al., 2020). Teachers delivering ineffective instruction result in lower student engagement levels and reduced academic achievement. To address these concerns, schools must provide opportunities for teacher in-service training to ensure that educators receive retraining, reskilling, and ongoing education necessary for the enhancement of knowledge. In order to

effectively educate students while managing occupational stressors experienced by faculty members—schools need resources capable of doing it.

Statement of the Problem

It has been noted that teachers effectiveness play crucial role in the educational process significantly influence human development and the overall functioning of society. This is because the quality of education is inextricably linked to the quality of educators, and every level of education must prepare and equip instructors with the necessary tools for successful instruction delivery. However, teachers are facing considerable occupational stress that negatively impacts their job performance, leading to underprepared graduates who struggle in future academic environments. The root causes of this stress include an unsupportive work environment, excessive workload, lack of instructional materials, delayed wages, inadequate training opportunities, disciplinary challenges among students, and personal financial burdens. Furthermore, some teachers struggle with assessment methods due to limited professional development support or poor interpersonal relations. Therefore, there is an urgent need for authorities implement research-based solutions, open communication, and feasible alternatives can help mitigate the negative outcomes of disproportionate stress. Identifying unmet necessities and providing proper management oversight can lead to better working conditions, ultimately benefiting the entire community. A commitment to transformational approaches is necessary to achieve equal success and empowerment, making everyone's life enjoyable, respected, and rewarding.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to examine occupational stress and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives:

- Determine the extent time management influences teachers job effectiveness in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
- Assess the extent excessive workload influences teachers job effectiveness in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
- Examine the extent lack of in-service training influences teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- To what extent does time management influences teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent does excessive workload influences teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent does lack of in-service training influences teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

To achieve the objectives of the study, the following null Hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between time management and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between lack of in-service training and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In 1979, Robert Karasek introduced the Demand-Control Theory. This theory has been extensively researched and remains highly relevant in the field of occupational stress. The central idea is that having control over work tasks can alleviate negative impacts caused by job demands on employees' well-being, increasing their satisfaction with challenging responsibilities and opportunities to acquire new skills (Karasek, 1979). According to Karasek's findings, two primary variables affect people's experience of stress within a working environment: job demands and decision latitude or autonomy - referring to how much agency workers have regarding task control. While high demand roles often involve significant psychological strain from tight deadlines or conflicting pressures due to external factors regularly impacting workflow performance negatively; greater amounts of decision-making power negate such strains when it comes amid overwhelming expectations. The theory emphasizes finding an optimal balance between job requirements versus levels of personal choice for successful outcomes without causing undue tension among colleagues experiencing more demanding situations but less say-so in handling them autonomously. This approach also reveals that individuals who feel powerless while facing intense challenges are at higher risk for burnout than those faced-up against low pressure-creage coupled with commanding positions meant reign supreme under such stressful conditions.

The demand-control theory suggests that a high-strain job results from having high-demand responsibilities with little to no decision-making latitude. Conversely, matching elevated tasks demands with increased control yields an active role and lowers stress levels while increasing fulfilment at work. Stress occurs when taxing expectations combine with limited opportunity for impact on procedures and obligations leading to negative employee health outcomes and dissatisfaction within the workplace. Factors which promote strain include heavy workload, inadequate rest breaks, long shifts or working hours along frenzied yet unfulfilling duties devoid of skill utilization or a sense of authority over proceedings. The perceived intensity of stresses may vary based upon aspects such as locus of control or self-efficacy; thereby indicating how possessing greater autonomy positively links higher satisfaction towards one's occupation consistently.

According to Karasek (1979), increased control can only alleviate stress if the individual has high self-efficacy. The demand-control theory has greatly impacted research on organizational stress and offers practical applications for workplace situations. This theory

suggests that when a person does not fit their environment, or vice versa, they will experience stress. For example, an overqualified employee may feel frustrated or bored in a certain job while someone lacking necessary skills may become overwhelmed. The relevance of this theory to education is clear: principals must make decisions that address specific scenarios and are relevant to staff members such as teachers and other stakeholders within secondary schools. By applying the demand-control theory within these contexts, it's possible for school administrators at all levels of hierarchy - from district superintendents down through local campus leaders – reduce teacher's stresses which would ultimately enhance their overall performance effectiveness in their jobs significantly with acceptance among subordinates/staff alike.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Occupational Stress

The term Stress is rooted in the Latin word “Stringere”, which means difficulty, pressure, challenge or distress. It impacts individuals physically, mentally, emotionally and spiritually resulting in a lower productivity level. Robinson (2007) defined stress as an external force that disrupts body's natural functioning due to unfavorable circumstances like teaching overload. These factors are known as stressors and excessive exposure of these can deplete confidence levels leading to reduced efficiency ultimately causing teachers to lose their interest from work affecting school environment at large positively or negatively. Stress on teachers' health results into emotional turmoil with physical implications such as headaches, stomach issues, inability concentrate, 'nervousness syndrome', insomnia, etc. ... Likewise contributing towards greater risk for heart illnesses including high blood pressure and stroke. Ending up either engaging them towards new opportunities by fighting against it hard enough else giving away succumbing themselves under immense mental duress Resultantly withdrawing oneself completely.

Occupational stress refers to the ongoing stress that arises from one's workplace, either due to responsibilities associated with the work itself or conditions based in working conditions. This type of stress can be triggered by unexpected responsibilities and can have a negative impact on an individual's ability to cope, particularly if they lack necessary training or skills. According to Humphrey (2008), occupational stress is emotional responses resulting from situations where job demands do not match worker capabilities, resources, or needs. Stressors are perceived as environmental pressures that exceed individuals' capacities (Topper, 2007; O'Neill & Palmer, 2004). Therefore, occupational stress encompasses both psychological and physical effects experienced by teachers due to their job duties within their environment and other pressures at work. It affects employees' mental health status soul well-being while also taking away some level of productivity which employers need for optimal output on jobs capabilities

Teachers

A teacher plays a vital role in providing structured and intentional guidance to their students. They serve as the shapers of young lives, holding significant influence over curriculum planning, development, and implementation (Dada, 1999). As primary agents for change within the education system, they play an essential part in achieving educational goals. The success of our schools particularly relies on teachers who are active, resourceful and skilled practitioners (Usha, 2013). Teachers act as intermediaries between policy-makers and learners facilitating translation

into action while applying knowledge-based principles interactively with their pupils (National Teachers Institute, 20011), ultimately placing them in a position that is indispensable when it comes to providing quality education.

According to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014), the quality and commitment of teachers determines how successful an educational system can be. The role of a teacher is vital in enabling effective teaching and learning since human capital drives socio-economic and political development within nations. Teachers are responsible for translating policies into action by implementing them during interactions with students. Effective educators not only deliver their curriculum efficiently but also ensure that students achieve optimum development through their approach to education.

Job Effectiveness

Job effectiveness is measured by the success in meeting objectives and solving targeted problems. The educational process relies heavily on teachers who are active, competent and resourceful (Usha, 2013). To evaluate the effectiveness of an education system, various factors must be considered including achieving school objectives, quality service delivery leading to student satisfaction; optimal utilization of available resources for effective feedback which serves as a basis for improvement or adjustment with regards to public needs. Teacher effectiveness involves employing teaching behaviors that encourage desired changes in students' learning processes.

The effectiveness of a teacher's job is determined by their ability to fulfill the duties outlined in their scheme of service. These include tasks such as lesson planning and preparation, delivery of lessons, punctuality and attendance at classes, evaluation of student progress, classroom management strategies, grading students' work amongst others. Umar (2018) stated that teachers are deemed effective when they successfully meet school objectives through meticulous attention paid to each aspect involved: creation of comprehensive schemes-of-work; thorough lesson-planning with detailed record-keeping practices; adept use-registers for learners enrolled in courses offered ; executing engaging classes featuring diverse teaching techniques suitable for varied learning styles complemented equally well with evaluation and assessment mechanisms approved by the institution. After school-hours involvement including but not limited to faculty meetings participation, responsible discipline-management policies implementation within classrooms coupled similarly encouraging campus-wide co-curricular activities ensuring proper mentoring/counselling on an individual basis if warranted so effortlessly contributes towards better overall execution abilities displayed portraying efficient educational professionals who aim high standards daily + helping shape young minds positively over extended period too!

The effectiveness of teachers' performance can be measured by their fulfillment of routine job responsibilities in schools. There are certain identifiable qualities that contribute to a teacher's success in the classroom, Wayne and Young (2003) noted them as qualifications, compensation, favorable working conditions with quality infrastructure and instructional materials, access to training opportunities and well-equipped libraries/laboratories. In addition to these factors lies intelligence level, attitude towards teaching profession, years of experience gathered from different institutions they have taught, respective academic degree obtained, personality traits coupled with mental stability which all impact on a teacher's efficacy within their roles (Raghu, 2004). A productive educator must strive for innovation while creating top-

tier services or products capable of keeping students engaged over time (Al-Zonbi, 2015). It is incumbent upon school principals/heads to unmask the motivational dynamics behind each staff member so as facilitate an enabling learning environment necessary for fostering lasting national development.

The National Policy of Education (2014) outlined the educational objectives for Nigeria, aimed at instilling national consciousness and unity, promoting values that are essential to individual and societal survival, imparting knowledge about one's environment while developing relevant skills as well as mental, physical and social competencies required for living a fulfilling life. The end result being an empowered citizen able to contribute towards the development of their community, because the achievement of educational goals is paramount, and it is crucial for teachers to be effective in their jobs. Therefore, measuring a variety of teaching aspects such as subject knowledge, communication skills, lesson preparation and presentation are all part of assessing teacher job effectiveness—making it a multidimensional construct (Okafor & Anaduaka, 2013).

Time Management and Teachers' Job Effectiveness

Scheerens and Callister (2014) defined time management as the process of reviewing resources and their transformation within a predetermined timeframe. Achieving maximum output within this time involves prioritizing tasks, estimating techniques, effective planning with do lists that prioritize top tasks to maximize use of available time, setting deadlines for greater productivity while avoiding external influences. A good teacher carefully plans their lessons so that they can cover everything within the time allocated for each lesson. Time management is a skill that teachers develop through constant practice, and it's often said that if you can manage your time well as a teacher, then you can do the same in life generally. Alike (2018) argued that success in life hinges on using one's time effectively: this means analyzing what needs to be done logically and making deductions accordingly. While teaching itself is important, doing it at the right moment - or "actual" time - makes all of the difference; after all, timing separates awareness from monotony and highlights which tasks have value versus those we could easily do without. Ultimately then, educators' ability to deliver timely instruction has an enormous impact on how effective they are overall in fulfilling their role as instructors!

Collaborating efficiently with other stakeholders is essential for teachers to navigate changes in curriculum and regulations. Schools tend to modify their schedules frequently, often without prior notification. As a result of this dynamism, educators have an obligation to actively engage in ongoing professional development and teach new material effectively. By implementing effective time management skills, they can alleviate stress levels while minimizing unnecessary expenditures of resources - all evidence that streamlining operations helps optimize proactivity and overall organization within the profession. Strategies for effective time management to enhance teachers job effectiveness include:

Prioritizing their work: To achieve this, it is necessary to prioritize tasks and organize them based on their significance. This entails completing the most critical and urgent task before moving on to less important ones (Scheerene, 2014). Such an approach enables teachers to work systematically while remaining pragmatic. Additionally, it facilitates a coherent evaluation of completed work within a defined timeframe.

Discipline: Teaching ethics encompasses work discipline, which involves adhering to the allotted time for completing tasks. This type of discipline can be viewed as a teacher's ability to manage their time effectively and is achieved through monitoring (Lavy, 2015). Self-monitoring plays an integral role in a teacher's display of work discipline by instilling self-awareness that directs them towards achieving goals within set timelines. Moreover, it encourages teachers not to exceed the specified task performance duration while operating within designated time limits.

Breaking lessons into periods or time: Teachers can utilize this as a method for managing their time effectively. Depending on the school's policy or regulations from governing bodies, educators may divide lessons or activities into 40-45 minute segments per period. This requires teachers to commence and conclude each task within the allocated timeframe—demonstrating their proficiency in meeting deadlines serving as an indicator of effectiveness (Ogunbaneni, 2018).

Effective time management is crucial for teachers to ensure optimal performance in both their personal and professional lives. Poor time management skills can directly impact a teacher's ability to manage tasks, leading to inefficiency and disorganization. Therefore, effective time management should be one of the key factors assessed when evaluating the effectiveness of a teacher. Moreover, implementing an efficient system for managing time boosts morale within educational institutions while building confidence among educators by creating opportunities for greater organization and outstanding achievements throughout their career development. With good strategies in place, occupational work stress decreases substantially—leading towards making sound decisions at critical moments with minimized confusions or misinterpretations happening amongst colleagues. In essence, developing essential practice methods that promote better utilization of available resources including quality output delivery capabilities enhance productivity levels as well.

Excessive workload And Teachers' Job Effectiveness

The workload of teachers in public senior secondary schools has a significant impact on their ability to perform effectively. This includes the amount of time spent working, as well as factors like class size and number of classes taught by each teacher. Many educators face challenges such as managing large student populations, handling administrative tasks, and meeting performance standards that can lead to excessive stress and exhaustion (Rose & Sika, 2019). Such pressure may result in decreased focus or motivation among teaching professionals starting both lower efficiency rates alongside compromised education quality for students too (Hester et al., 2020). Moreover, an unmanageable level workloads triggers burnout amongst these educators thus affects not only personal health but also professional wellbeing (Mullen et al., 2020). Teacher burnout is a known related-factor towards career dissatisfaction, increasing employee turnover ratios within this line over-time which further aggravates skill gaps felt tangibly across numerous geographical locations globally.

It is crucial that public schools prioritize the effective management of teacher workload and provide necessary resources for student education (Balang, 2021). When teachers are overloaded with various responsibilities and teaching hours, they may feel overwhelmed by their school's demands leading to reduced motivation and efficacy. Obi (2004) noted that excessive workloads can result in stress which presents itself as poor concentration, fatigue, and difficulty

making decisions; if unchecked this situation could lead to collapse leaving them unable to effectively fulfil job duties. To combat these challenges, teachers must adopt active time-management strategies alongside delegating tasks through collaboration with colleagues for optimal performance efficiency. School leaders should take steps towards reducing the overwhelming work burden on teachers by decreasing class sizes and offering administrative support through teaching assistants. Additionally, mental well-being of educators must be prioritized in public schools with proper resources to avoid exhaustion.

In-service Training and Teachers' Job Effectiveness

The process of training teachers involves instilling knowledge and skills to enhance their ability to teach effectively both within and beyond the classroom. Adequate and regular retraining is indispensable for a functional educational system, supporting effective teaching outcomes. Teachers must be kept abreast with technological advancements in education management through on-going learning opportunities that enable updates on current practices. Akpakwu (2008) identified different teacher training programs—including seminars, conferences, workshops, revision courses, another approach include designed to improve job performance effectiveness. In-service training refers to a variety of courses and activities available for working teachers seeking to improve their professional knowledge, skills, and teaching competency. This type of education encompasses all forms of training programs designed specifically for educators already on the job. Undertaking in-service training allows teachers to perform more efficiently and effectively in their roles.

Participating in in-service training programs sensitizes teachers to contemporary methods of assessing student performance and facilitates collaboration among them to tackle shared challenges. These sessions equip educators with the skills necessary for utilizing cutting-edge technology through access and use of information and communication tools, enabling them to develop self-confidence, enhance leadership abilities, and foster effective classroom management techniques. It is thus essential that teachers attend such events regularly as they evolve alongside changes within their field while maintaining expertise relevant to imparting valuable knowledge, aptitudes, and competencies.

Benefits of In-Service Training to Teachers

The following benefits will accrue to teachers on account of in- service training as outlined by Okeke (2004) as:

- It enables teachers to obtain his/her qualifications (professional and academic).
- It enables teachers acquire more conceptual and technical knowledge and pedagogy, in order to improve on their efficiency in class instruction.
- It improves social and academic status of teachers in the society.
- It helps teachers to keep in touch with their counterparts within and outside the country in terms of intellectual mobility.

Insufficient in-service training opportunities in public secondary schools often impede teacher effectiveness (Shaibu & Isah, 2018). When teachers are deprived of adequate chances to update their knowledge through workshops and seminars, or learn effective teaching methods, it

becomes a challenge for them to perform effectively. This issue has a direct impact on the quality of education provided in public secondary institutions.

Conference, Seminars and Workshops

These serve as channels for educators to update their professional knowledge and stay abreast of current trends within their field, providing opportunities to learn about emerging discoveries while facing challenges. Unfortunately, teachers may struggle with financial constraints when attempting to attend these events due to meager salaries which limit self-sponsorship capacity. Okeke (2004) proposed that teacher salary scales be periodically adjusted in accordance with the cost of living so as not leave them at a disadvantage; this adjustment could enable attendance at conferences even without government support. It is crucial for teachers to stay up-to-date with educational issues and developments through seminars and workshops in order to enhance their professional development. These events provide opportunities for interaction, collaboration, and problem-solving among educators. It is also important that the government regularly creates platforms where teachers can share knowledge on specific topics, such as lesson preparation or student report writing. In-service training programs like these are intended to improve pedagogy skills among teaching professionals.

Ways of Boosting Teachers' Effectiveness in Schools

According to Nakpodia (2011), teachers' effectiveness can be boosted in the following ways:

Clear Line of communication: To comprehend the challenges confronting their school, it is essential for every administrator to be informed. It's advisable to seek input or feedback from staff members and also encourage collaborative management within the school setting.

Be visible: Search for chances to increase your visibility within your school as frequently as you can. This elevates the spirits and efficiency of educators in fulfilling their responsibilities, especially if you warmly greet any staff members encountered along the way and engage them in conversing person-to-person.

Develop and define a sound reward system: Explore methods to create a fair compensation plan for educators that does not prioritize market variables over equity. Additionally, consider implementing incentives for non-teaching personnel such as offering additional administrative assistance or providing opportunities for professional development and travel allowances.

Appreciate every good work: Express your gratitude towards the hard work of teachers and other school staff. Show appreciation by sending personalized thank you notes. If financial problems arise, acknowledge that they are being productive and appreciate their assistance in finding solutions to budgetary issues.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted in this study was correlational, which aimed to investigate the relationships between two variables without manipulation by the researcher. The population for

this study consisted of 6,839 teachers (3,333 male and 3,224 female) from 302 public senior secondary schools located in Rivers State. A simple random sampling technique was utilized to select a sample size of 656 participants or roughly ten percent of the total population drawn from these institutions. Researchers employed an original questionnaire developed specifically for data collection called "Occupational Stress and Teachers' Job Effectiveness (OSTJEQ)". This instrument contained two sections: Section A gathered demographic information while Section B corresponded with three specific areas explored throughout this research endeavor using twelve separate questions utilizing a four-point Likert rating scale ranging across Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extenet (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE). Also, this tool underwent modification following testing its reliability through Cronbach Alpha estimation producing satisfactory results showing .78 co-efficient. Generally speaking, outside those discarded during filtering based on invalid responses, a landfall amounting up-to=seven-hundred-and-thirty questionnaires were distributed out-of-which only six hundred thirty-seven got considered valid, following careful analysis. Less-over, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient performed at a statistical significance level set as low as p-value .05 helped verify anticipated correlations observed via mean values and standard Deviation calculations. The researcher accomplished all necessary computations relying upon the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does time management influence teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of the extent to which time management influences teachers’ job effectiveness

Items	N	Mean	SD.	Remark
1. I feel that I have enough time to complete my tasks	637	2.973	1.034	High Extent
2. I feel that my time is being used efficiently	637	2.989	1.060	High Extent
3. I feel rushed or overwhelmed	637	3.064	.902	High Extent
4. I feel that my time management skills are adequate to meet the demands of my job	637	3.002	1.014	High Extent
Grand Mean	637	3.007		High Extent

Research question one analyzed to what extent time management influences teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and a grand mean of 3.01 was obtained which is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. Based on the grand mean of 3.007, the result indicates that most of the respondents agree to a high extent that time management influences teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: To what extent does excessive workload influence teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of the extent to which excessive workload influences teachers’ job effectiveness

Items	N	Mean	SD.	Remark
5. I keep in the background and do not display overbearing attitude	637	3.223	.882	High Extent
6. I am very sociable and exhibit high level of energetic behaviours and activities	637	3.407	3.118	High Extent
7. I love to make people happy	637	3.113	.954	High Extent
8. I do not talk a lot and therefore do not say things that bring chaos	637	2.994	.989	High Extent
Grand Mean	637	3.185		High Extent

Research question two analyzed to what extent excessive workload influences teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and a grand mean of 3.18 was obtained which is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. Based on the grand mean of 3.18, the result indicates that most of the respondents agree to a high extent that excessive workload influences teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Research Question 3: To what extent does lack of in-service training influence teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of the extent to which lack of in-service training influences teachers’ job effectiveness

Items	N	Mean	SD.	Remark
9. I feel that I have adequate training and support to do my job effectively	637	2.973	1.034	High Extent
10. I feel that I am able to keep up with changes in the field of education	637	2.989	1.060	High Extent
11. I feel that I have the skills and knowledge needed to meet the needs of my students	637	3.064	.902	High Extent
12. I feel that I have the support of my school administration in my professional development	637	3.002	1.014	High Extent
Grand Mean	637	3.007		High Extent

Research question three analysed to what extent lack of in-service training influences teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and a grand mean of 3.07 was obtained which is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. Based on the grand mean of 3.07, the result indicates that most of the respondents agree to a high extent that lack of in-service training influences teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between time management and teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Analysis of relationship between time management and teachers job effectiveness

		Time management	Teachers job effectiveness
Time management	Pearson Correlation	1	.529**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	637	637
Teachers job effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.529**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	637	637

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 shows the relationship between time management and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients. From the analysis, the result showed the correlation coefficient of $r = 0.529$ was obtained which shows the direction and strength of this relationship indicating that there is a strong positive correlation between time management and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The tests of significance show that this relationship is significant at $p .000 < .05$ which makes possible the generalization of our findings to the study population. Therefore, based on observed findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a strong positive and significant relationship between time management and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: Analysis of the relationship between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness

		Excessive Workload	Teachers' Job Effectiveness
Excessive Workload	Pearson Correlation	1	.572**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	637	637
Teachers' job effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.572**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	637	637

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 shows the relationship between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients. From the analysis, the result showed the correlation coefficient of $r = 0.572$ was obtained which shows the direction and strength of this relationship indicating that there is a strong positive correlation between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The tests of significance show that this relationship is significant at $p .001 < .05$ which makes possible the generalization of our findings to the study population. Therefore, based on observed findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a strong positive and significant relationship between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between lack of in-service training and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: Analysis of the relationship between lack of in-service training and teachers' job effectiveness

		Lack of in-service training	Teachers' job effectiveness
Lack of in-service training	Pearson Correlation	1	.639**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	637	639
Teachers' job effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.639**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	637	637

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 shows the relationship between lack of in-service training and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients. From the analysis, the result showed the correlation coefficient of $r = 0.639$ was obtained which shows the direction and strength of this relationship indicating that there is a strong positive correlation between lack of in-service training and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The tests of significance show that this relationship is significant at $p .000 < .05$ which makes possible the generalization of our findings to the study population. Therefore, based on observed findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a strong positive and significant relationship between the lack of in-service training and teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Time Management and Teachers' Job Effectiveness

The second hypothesis explored the relationship between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Rivers State. Contrary to the proposed hypothesis, the findings revealed a strong positive correlation between excessive workload and teacher job performance, with an r -value of $.529$ and a P -value of $.000 < 0.05\%$. This suggests that teachers who manage excessive workloads effectively tend to perform exceptionally well in their roles. However, excessive workload can lead to increased stress levels, reduced concentration, and eventual exhaustion (Obi, 2004). To address this, it is essential to promote active time management skills and group collaboration among teachers. This can help educators manage heavy workloads more efficiently, leading to improved job performance and ultimately, better educational outcomes. To achieve educational excellence, it is crucial to implement measures that support teachers in managing excessive workloads. This can be achieved through district-wide initiatives that promote best practices, provide resources, and foster a culture of collaboration and support. By doing so, educators can unlock their full potential, and students can benefit from improved academic success. Ultimately, this contributes to a vibrant and thriving educational community, where everyone can flourish and reach their aspirations.

Excessive Workload and Teachers' Job Effectiveness

The second hypothesis aimed to investigate the connection between excessive workload and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools located within Rivers State. It was proposed that there would be no notable correlation identified between excessive workload and teacher job performance. The results indicated a strong positive relationship portrayed by teachers' exceptional job functionality when confronted with heavy workloads at an r-value of .572, P-value = .000 < .05%. These results align with Obi's (2004) observations where increased stress levels became apparent due to excess workloads resulting in reduced concentration abilities leading up exhaustion difficulties while making decisions associated directly linked inadequate workplace efficiency or operation capability of these individuals affected.

Lack of In-Service Training and Teachers' Job Effectiveness

The third hypothesis aimed to explore the correlation between insufficient in-service training and job effectiveness among secondary school teachers in Rivers State. The hypothesis proposed that no significant relationship exists between the lack of in-service training and teachers' ability to perform their duties effectively. However, the results revealed a strong positive connection, with a P-value of .000 < .05% and an r-value of .572, indicating a significant relationship between the two variables. This finding supports the stance which highlighted the adverse effects of inadequate education on teacher efficiency. The lack of opportunities for professional development, such as updated knowledge and skills through seminars or workshops, reduces productivity and teaching quality, leading to below-average performance levels over time (Okeke, 2004). Moreover, Okeke emphasized that updating one's understanding professionally reduces stress and enables better performances, allowing teachers to adapt positively to developments and job enhancements. This can be achieved through conferences and workshops funded by adjusted salaries, highlighting the importance of investing in teachers' professional development to enhance their job effectiveness and overall educational outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the study indicated that occupational stress adversely affects teachers' job effectiveness. The correlation between lack of time management, excessive workload and inadequate in-service training with occupational stress was found to be highly significant as per the responses received from respondents. These findings have great importance for this research project; hence it is essential to tackle these problems if we want to improve teacher's well-being and their overall efficacy at work.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher makes the following recommendations:

- Increasing the hours of a school day can assist policymakers and educators in dedicating more time to professional duties such as lesson planning, grading assignments etc. This measure may also decrease teachers' workload after regular hours while improving their job contentment and overall performance.

- To ease the burden on teachers, school administrators ought to minimize paperwork and other non-essential duties. They can achieve this by simplifying or removing needless bureaucracy or offering supplementary administrative assistance for activities such as reporting and entering data.
- School administrators ought to enhance the quantity of professional development chances presented to educators, tailoring them in accordance with the specific requirements of teachers. For instance, schools may hold workshops that introduce novel teaching methodologies or technology and allow instructors enough time for sharing one another's best practices.

REFERENCES

- Akinboye, J. O., Akinboye, D. O., Adeyemo, D. A. (2002). *Coping with stress in life and workplace*. Stirling-Horden Publishers.
- Akpakwu, O.S (2008). *Essentials of educational management*. Jalim Press.
- Alike, A. E. (2018). *Report on performance, patterns and trends in teaching primary school in Owerri*. Totan Publishers.
- Al-Zoubi, S. M. (2015). *Time management and planning strategies in public primary schools in Kaduna States*. Abdul-Rahman Publishers.
- Balang, N. J. (2021). Elements of teacher readiness in the construct of special education teacher workload in Malaysia. *Turkish Journal of Computer & Mathematics Education*, 12(11), 5269-5273.
- Dada (1999). *The teacher and the curriculum*. Tejama Enterprises.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education* (6th Edition). National Education Research Council Press.
- Hester, O. R., Bridges, S. A., & Rollins, L. H. (2020). Overworked and underappreciated': special education teachers describe stress and attrition. *Teacher Development*, 24(3), 348-365.
- Humphrey, J. H. (2008). *Job stress*. Allyn & Bacon.
- Karasek Jr., R. A. (1979). Job demands, job decision latitude, and mental strain: Implications for job redesign. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24, 285-308. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2392498>.
- Lavy, W. D. (2015). *Practicum in classroom organization and management*. Cape Publishers.
- Mullen, R., Backer, A., Chae, N., & Li, H. (2020). School counselors' work-related rumination as predictor of burnout, turnover intentions, job satisfaction, work engagement. *Professional School Counseling*, 24(1), 2156759X20957253.
- Nakpodia, E. D. (2011). The dependent outcome of teachers' performance in secondary schools in Delta State: An empirical assessment of principal's supervision capacity. *African Journal of Education and Technology*, 1(1), 15-24.
- National Teachers Institute (2011). *Manual for the training of junior secondary school teachers*. NTI Press.
- O'Neill, M. A., & Palmer, A. (2004). *Importance-performance analysis: a useful tool for directing continuous quality improvement in higher education*. Quality assurance in education. Son Press.
- Obi, E. (2004). *Issues in educational administration*. Empathy International and J Publications.

- Ogunbanaem, F. N. (2014). *Principles of good time manage skills in an organization* (2nd Ed). Prentice Hall.
- Okafor, C. F., & Anaduaka, U. S. (2013). Nigerian school children and mathematics phobia: How the mathematics teacher can help. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 1(7), 247-251.
- Okeke, B. S. (2004). *Teaching in Nigeria: The bureaucracy and professionalization*. Mercury Int'l Publishing.
- Raghu, D. V. K. (2004). *A study of teacher's stress in relation to teacher effectiveness and attitude*. Unpublished PhD Thesis. University Press.
- Robinson, M. (2007). *Stress: Chamber's 21st century dictionary*. Allied Chambers.
- Rose, A. B., & Sika, J. O. (2019). Determining influence of teacher's workload on academic performance in secondary schools, Suba Sub-County Kenya. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 6(3), 287-295.
- Scheerens, T. F., & Callister, W. D. (2014). *Chart on time management variables and its application in schools*. Pergamon.
- Topper, E. F. (2007). Stress in the library. *Journal of New Library*, 108(11/12), 561-564.
- Umar, D. (2018). *Principals' instructional supervision and teachers' performance of secondary schools in Danko Wasagu Local Government Area, Kebbi State, North-West Nigeria*. Published Thesis. Kampala International University Press.
- UNESCO. (2004). *EFA Global Monitoring Report 2005: Education for all the quality imperative*. UNESCO.
- Usha, A. B. (2013). A study of teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to teacher stress. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2(12), 13-16.